

Electromagnetic Field Environment in a Typical Hospital

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Abstract—The increase of electromagnetic fields sources in susceptible environments, such as hospitals, has led to researchers around the world to quantify the potential risk of electromagnetic interference on medical equipment. To reduce risks in these equipments, it is important to know the electromagnetic field environment that can be found in the hospitals and clinics. In this paper, the results of electromagnetic field measurements, both low and high frequency, carried out in different departments of a large hospital are presented. The results show that power frequency magnetic field in some rooms was higher than immunity test levels established by international standard for medical devices. However, the high frequency electric field environment in all rooms measured was lower than international standard.

Keywords—power frequency; magnetic field; high frequency; electric field; hospital.

I. INTRODUCTION

Since the 70s, there was a concern about the effects of electromagnetic interferences (IEMs) in hospitals. In 1979, the Food and Drug Administration issued a rule entitled "Electromagnetic Compatibility Standard for Medical Devices" [1]. This rule dealt with the general aspects of IEMs, taking into account both conducted and radiated emissions, and established susceptibility tests to electric fields, magnetic fields, and transient.

Since then, several studies began to treat the problems of electromagnetic interferences and medical equipments. One of the studies with the greatest impact on this topic was developed by Silberberg [2]. In this study, were presented over a hundred cases related to electromagnetic interferences in medical equipments. All cases based on reports received by FDA between 1979 and 1993.

After verification of interferences in medical equipments, the following studies [3], [4] focused on characterizing the electromagnetic environment of hospitals. Most of the studies measured high-frequency electric field levels and identified the influence of sources outside the hospital, especially those related to communication systems such as radio and TV broadcasters, and mobile telephony. However, few works [5], [6] have been performed to characterize the power frequency magnetic environment of hospitals.

The hospital power supply is an inside source of power frequency magnetic fields. This electrical installation is designed to supply all the devices, including medical equipments. However, an electric wire through which current is flowing generates a magnetic field around it. The magnetic field magnitude is proportional to the amount of current. In a large hospital, the number of medical devices is rapidly increasing. Therefore, the demand for electricity is growing. This means that an increase in the amount of current will produce an increase in the magnetic field strength inside the hospital.

A high level of electric or magnetic field could be affecting the adequate operation of medical equipments [7]. Therefore, it is necessary evaluate the high frequency electric field and power frequency magnetic field levels in the different rooms and areas of the hospitals. This will permit to know if medical devices are operating in a "safe" environment.

In this paper the results of the high-frequency electric field and power frequency magnetic field levels measured in a hospital are presented. The measurements were carried out in order to characterize the electromagnetic environment of the hospital. The measurement results were compared with the levels set in the IEC 60601-1-2 standard [8]. This standard specifies high frequency immunity levels (80-2500 MHz) of 3 V/m for non-life support equipments, and 10 V/m for life support equipments. On the other hand, the standard states that medical equipment should work normally in a 3 A/m power frequency magnetic field (approximately 37.7 mG).

II. METHODOLOGY

In a large area with several sources, the best way to evaluate the spatial variation of the electric or magnetic field is using the method of mapping. This method consists of making a path along the site to identify the zones with the same values. The values are then displayed in a contour map or a 3D map.

High frequency electric field and power frequency magnetic field measurements were carried out in different rooms of seven departments of the Foundation Clinic Valle del Lili, as indicated in Table I. Because most of the measurement areas were in operation, the measurement process were quite

complex. It was necessary to handle high levels of asepsis and not bother to patients. For this reason, measurements were made at different times and on different days, once it was received the authorization by the hospital staff.

TABLE I. ROOMS MEASURED

No.	Department	Number of rooms measured
1	Surgery (S)	16
2	Neonatal ICU (NICU)	2
3	Pediatric ICU (PICU)	31
4	Adult ICU (AICU)	31
5	Recovery – adult (RA) ^a	19
6	Clinical laboratory I (CLI)	15
7	Clinical laboratory II (CLII)	14
Total		128

a. Only the magnetic field was measured

A. High frequency electric field

The measurements were carried out by using the EMR-300 meter with the Type 18 probe. The EMR-300 is a radiofrequency electric field strength meter for broadband measurement and monitoring in different frequency ranges. The isotropic non-directional field Type 18 probe with high sensitivity records electric field in 100 kHz – 3 GHz frequency range covering the most typical frequencies in telecommunications and industrial applications. The Type 18 probe has a range of 0.2 V/m to 320 V/m, and an absolute error of ± 1.0 dB.

First, in the different areas that are part of the department, several profiles were measured in order to obtain the contour map of each room. Then, the contour maps of each room were joined to create a map of the entire department. In each of the rooms, the rms values of the electric field in all spatial directions (x, y, z) were measured. For each profile, the electric field was recorded every 2.0 seconds and at a height of 1 meter above ground level. On average, three data were recorded each meter.

To view contour maps derived from the electromagnetic field measurements recorded by the EMR-300 meter, an application was developed in Matlab using the v4 interpolation method. This method showed better results compared with the other three methods (linear, cubic, and nearest) when comparing the contour maps with those generated by a commercial tool (EMCALC 2007) for graphing and analyzing data recorded by the low frequency magnetic field EMDEX II meter. In Fig. 1 the four profiles measured and the 3D map of high frequency electric field obtained in a room of the surgery department is showed.

B. Power frequency magnetic field

A gauss meter (EMDEX II) was used for measurements. Three coils are arranged inside the unit to record the magnetic flux density of each axis (B_x, B_y, B_z) of the probe according to (1). The microprocessor instantly calculates the resultant magnetic field from magnetic field readings of each axis. The EMDEX II meter has a resolution of 0.1 mG, a range of 0.1-3000 mG, and a 1% full-scale accuracy.

$$B = \sqrt{B_x^2 + B_y^2 + B_z^2} \quad (1)$$

First, in each of the different rooms that are part of the department, the magnetic field measurement was carried out in order to obtain the contour map of this small area. Then, the contour maps of each room were joined to generate a map of the entire department. In each of the rooms, the rms values of the magnetic field X, Y and Z components were measured. At each point, the measurements were carried out each 1.5 seconds and at a height of 1 meter above ground level. On average, three data were recorded each meter.

For the analysis of the results was used EMCALC 2007 software. This software allows displaying data recorded with the EMDEX II meter in field versus distance graphs and contour maps. In Fig. 2 the path followed and the magnetic field contour map obtained in a room (pathology) of clinical laboratory is showed.

Figure 1. Profiles measured and electric field 3D map of a surgery room

Figure 2. Path and magnetic field contour map of a room

Figure 6. Maximum and mean magnetic field measured in the clinic

As shown in Fig. 6, magnetic field levels higher than IEC standard were found in two departments: Clinical Laboratory II and Adult ICU. In Clinical Laboratory was measured a 103.7-mG magnetic field in a small room with large medical equipments used in infectious tests. This magnetic field strength is about three times higher than the value established by the IEC.

In the Adult ICU, the highest level measured was 54.7 mG and it was found in a room with several medical equipments working simultaneously. This magnetic field exceeded in about 200% the established level by the IEC. In other departments, the magnetic field levels measured were lower than immunity levels set by international standards.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The high frequency electric field and power frequency magnetic field environment in seven big areas of a hospital were measured. In all rooms, the strengths found were below radio frequency radiated immunity level for medical equipments established at the IEC standard. However, in two rooms were measured values higher than 60 Hz radiated immunity level for medical equipments. In these areas, malfunctions could occur with some medical equipment.

In both cases it was not possible to say with certainty what was the source that generated the described field levels. This is

because the time available for measurements in each room was very short, and it was not possible to perform a more detailed analysis in each room.

It is very important to assess the electric and magnetic field level in the rooms of a hospital before installing a medical equipment to ensure proper operation and prevent future problems. Other areas of hospitals also need to be measured (e.g. emergency room) to complete an entire map of the hospital electromagnetic environment.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors thank Johanna Silva, Carlos A. López, and Jhon E. Ramírez for your help with the measurement campaigns.

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